

The Use of Digital Twins for the Management of Cultural Heritage Sites

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There is a need for the use of digital twins of cultural heritage sites, especially for those that are affected by natural hazards, for documentation, monitoring and management. This study examines the use of digital twins through the EXCELSIOR and TRIQUETRA project for the use of 3D digital volumetric representation model and Augmented Reality applications by creating a digital twin for monitoring natural hazards in archaeological settings. The EXCELSIOR H2020 Widespread Teaming project under Grant Agreement No 857510 and the TRIQUETRA project Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101094818 will study the effects of climate change and natural hazards on cultural heritage and remediation using state-of-the-art techniques. Through the TRIQUETRA project, Choirokoitia, Cyprus is used as one of the pilot studies using these techniques. Choirokoitia is a UNESCO World Heritage Site and is one of the best-preserved Neolithic sites in the Mediterranean. The project will also examine the potential risk of rockfall at the Choirokoitia site, as the topology of the site is vulnerable to movements as a result of extreme climate change as well as of daily/seasonal stressing actions. Rockfall poses a significant danger to visitor safety as well as damage to cultural heritage sites.

Digital twins provide a dynamic visualization of the site and can also be used to monitor any changes resulting from natural hazards. A digital twin model can also be shared with visitors in order to provide an alternative approach and a visualization experience for viewing the site.